

Title: A combinatorial mosaic of input-specific microdomains within the “higher-order relay” posterior thalamic nucleus of mice

Abbreviated title: Inputs to higher-order thalamus

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Abstract

A large part of the thalamus is not directly involved in relaying ascending sensory inputs to the cerebral cortex. The functions and wiring of such “non-primary” nuclei remain unclear. The Posterior nucleus, a representative “non-primary” nucleus of the rodent thalamus, receives heavy and powerful inputs from cortical layer 5 (L5) cells. In addition, Po receives also some trigeminal, spinal and superior colliculus (SC) inputs, as well as powerful inhibitory inputs from the zona incerta (ZI) and anterior pretectal nucleus (APT). To elucidate to which extent these input systems converge or remain separate within Po, we first mapped the distribution of terminals immunolabeled for markers of glutamatergic or GABAergic neurotransmission and L5 terminals constitutively labeled in Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 mice. Besides, we retrogradely traced and quantified the sources of brain and spinal cord input reaching different Po regions. In addition, we compared bouton sizes in axons anterogradely labeled from the above input sources. Our data delineate several domains within Po, each dominated by specific sets of inputs. Cortical L5 afferents predominate in central and ventral Po. In contrast, large glutamatergic terminals from the trigeminal complex and spinal cord as well as GABAergic terminals from APT and ZI prevail in rostral and dorsal Po, and along the border with the ventral posteromedial nucleus. SC inputs preferentially target dorsal and caudal Po. These findings reveal multiple partly overlapping domains within Po. Hence, thalamic neuron subpopulations in different parts of Po may integrate diverse combinations of tactile, motor and pain-related inputs and give rise to functionally diverse thalamocortical subnetworks.

Significance statement

Many nuclei of the thalamus are not involved in relaying to cortex new information about the world or the body. The functions and wiring of such “non-primary” nuclei remain unclear. Here, we first mapped across the brain and spinal cord the origin of the input pathways reaching the Posterior nucleus, a typical non-primary relay nucleus. Then, we analyzed input distribution within the nucleus and, as a proxy for synaptic strength, the size of their axon terminals. We report a complex tridimensional mosaic of partly overlapping input-specific domains and significant bouton size differences. This wiring may allow diverse inputs to converge in graded combinatorial fashion onto thalamic cell subpopulations, hence giving rise to emergent computations and functionally diverse thalamocortical subnetworks.

Introduction

Thalamic cells integrate and relay to other forebrain structures the inputs that they receive from a variety of cortical and subcortical sources. In every thalamic nucleus, content-defining signals are carried by pathways with highly effective synapses (“driver”). Considering the source of these “driver” inputs, thalamic nuclei have been classified into two broad categories: the “First-Order” (FO) nuclei are driven by subcortical inputs and send this information to cortex, and the “Higher-Order” (HO) nuclei are driven by cortical layer (L)5b projections and involved in cortico-thalamo-cortical pathways (Sherman and Guillery, 1998; Theyel et al., 2010).

The Posterior (Po) nucleus of the mouse thalamus is a model HO nucleus because it receives a robust L5b input and mediates transthalamic communication (Theyel et al., 2010; Guo et al., 2020). This L5b projection has been widely described for the barrel field of the primary somatosensory cortex (S1BF; Bourassa et al., 1995; Veinante et al., 2000b; Killackey and Sherman, 2003; Sumser et al., 2017; Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018; Hayashi et al., 2021). Terminals with driver characteristics in Po can also originate from other cortical structures, such as secondary somatosensory (S2; Liao et al., 2010) and motor cortices (Rouiller et al., 1991; Sampathkumar et al., 2021). HO nuclei additionally receive extra-thalamic inhibitory inputs (Halassa and Acsady, 2016). In addition to reticular thalamic input (TRN; Pinault et al., 1995), Po is innervated by inhibitory centers such as the zona incerta (ZI; Power et al., 1999; Bartho et al., 2002) and anterior pretectal nuclei (APT; Bokor et al., 2005).

However, despite being considered a model HO nucleus, Po also receives brainstem and spinal inputs and it is involved in somatosensory information processing. Po axons convey information mainly about timing/amplitude differences between ongoing cortical outputs and multi-whisker sensory signals, which may be important for computing object location (Yu et al., 2006; Masri et al., 2008; Ahissar and Oram, 2015). Po receives most of its ascending projections from neurons in the interpolaris spinal trigeminal nuclei (SpVI; Jacquin et al., 1989; Pierret et al., 2000; Veinante et al., 2000a) and thus have driver characteristics (Lavallee et al., 2005). In addition, other subcortical structures such as dorsal column nuclei (DCN; Lund and Webster, 1967; Uemura et al., 2020) and the spinal cord (Iwata et al., 1992; Gauriau and Bernard, 2004) also project to Po, at least in rats.

Although driver afferents can arise from both the cortex and subcortical centers, their exact distribution within the HO thalamic nuclei is largely unknown and the existence of subnetworks within individual thalamic nuclei remain under debate (Roy et al., 2022). Some data on this topic has been provided by Rovo et al., (2012), who mapped the macaque thalamus using vesicular glutamate transporter type 1 (vGLUT1) and type 2 (vGLUT2) to label cortical and subcortical afferents, respectively. This study demonstrated the co-distribution of cortical and subcortical terminals is limited and usually located on the borders between FO and HO nuclei. In addition, more recent studies have shown that different driver inputs can even converge and interact onto individual thalamic neurons, as superior colliculus (SC) and retinal terminals in the lateral geniculate nucleus (Bickford, 2015) and cortical L5b and ascending somatosensory inputs in Po (Groh et al., 2014). However, it remains unclear to which extent this is the case throughout HO nuclei, since the origin and terminal distribution of afferent connections have not been mapped in a systematic manner.

Here, we used immunocytochemistry and transgenic Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 mice to examine the distribution of excitatory and inhibitory terminals within Po, a representative HO nucleus of the mouse thalamus. In addition, using retrograde axonal tracing in adult mice, we mapped throughout the entire neuroaxis the source and relative numbers of cells innervating different portions of Po. Finally, high-resolution BDA anterograde tracing was used to analyze the synaptic bouton sizes of Po input pathways. Our results delineate several domains within Po, each dominated by specific sets of inputs.

Materials and Methods

Animals

Experiments were performed on adult (60-120 days old, 25-35 g body weight) wild-type C57BL/6 mice of both sexes. Animals were bred in the Animal Facilities of the School of Medicine of the Autónoma de Madrid University. All procedures involving live animals were conducted under protocols approved by the university Ethics Committee and the competent Regional Government agency (PROEX175/16), in accordance with the European Community Council Directive 2010/63/UE. Animals were housed under standard colony conditions with food and water *ad libitum* under a 12 h light/dark cycle. Efforts were made to minimize the number of animals required. In total, twenty-six mice were used for retrograde tracing experiments, forty-two were used for anterograde BDA axon labeling and five further mice were used for immunolabeling analyses.

In addition, the brains from two mice from the L5 Cre-expressing Rbp4-Cre: Ai14 strain (Gong et al., 2007) were used to examine the distribution of cortical L5 pyramidal cell axons within Po. Procedures to obtain these two brains were performed in the animal facilities of the University of Oxford (UK) under a valid Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 project license as well as with local ethical approval by the Central Committee on Animal Care and Ethical Review (ACER) and the Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Body (AWERB) at the University of Oxford. Tg(Rbp4cre)KL100Gsat/Mmucd (Rbp4-Cre; Jackson Laboratories) mice were crossed with B6;129S6-Gt(ROSA)26Sortm14(CAG-tdTomato)Hze/J (Ai14) to constitutively drive fluorescent protein expression in cortical L5 pyramidal neurons (Hayashi et al., 2021).

Anesthetic procedures

In the tracing experiments with post-injection survival, anesthesia was induced with an intraperitoneal injection of ketamine (0.075 mg/g body weight) + xylazine (0.02 mg/g body weight), and subsequently maintained throughout the surgical procedure with isoflurane in oxygen (0.5-1 %). At the end of the surgery, isoflurane was interrupted, and animals recovered promptly. Ibuprofen (120 mg/L) was added to the drinking water to ensure analgesia during the post-operative period.

At the time of sacrifice, animals were overdosed with sodium pentobarbital (0.09 mg/g body weight, i.p.).

Retrograde axonal tracer experiments

Retrograde tracers were microinjected in the thalamus to map across the brain and spinal cord the neuronal populations targeting specific thalamic nuclei. Animals were positioned in a stereotaxic apparatus (David Kopf Instruments, Tujunga, CA, USA) and placed on a water-heated pad at 37 °C. The scalp was sectioned at the midline and retracted, and small craniotomies were opened in the parietal bones. Two different retrograde fluorescent tracers, one in each hemisphere, were injected through borosilicate glass micropipettes (WPI, Sarasota, FL, USA; outer tip diameter: 10–15 µm), positioned under stereotaxic guidance either in Po (Bregma 1.8 mm posterior, 1.2 mm lateral, and 3.2 mm ventral; Paxinos and Franklin, 2012) or in VPM (- 1.7, 1.7 and 3.3 mm, respectively). The tracers used were Fast Blue (FB; diamidino compound 253/50, Polysciences Europe GmbH, Eppelheim, Germany; 0.1 % w/vol. in 0.1 M cacodylate buffer; pH 7.4) or Fluoro-Gold (FG; hydroxystilbamidine methanesulfonate H-22845, Molecular Probes Fluorochrome LLC, Denver, CO, USA; 0.75% w/vol. in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, PB). FB was pressure-injected (0.01- 0.1 µl) using a precision electro-valve system (Picospritzer II, Parker Hannifin, Cleveland, OH, USA) while FG was microiontophoresized with a Midgard Precision Current Source Cat N°. 51590 (Stoelting, Wood Dale, IL, USA) by applying 4–5 µA positive continuous current cycles (7 s on/off) for 3–5 min. Pipettes were left in place for 10 minutes after the injection, before being removed. Finally, muscle and skin were disinfected with povidone iodine and sutured, and the animals were allowed to recover and returned to their cage.

Anterograde axonal transport experiments

To label axon terminals from the populations identified by the retrograde tracing experiments, lysine-fixable 10 kDa biotinylated dextran amine (BDA; Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA; 3% w/v solution in 0.01 M PB, pH 7.4) was selectively iontophoretically injected in different regions of the forebrain, brainstem or spinal cord. A positive current was applied using a Dual Current 260 source (World Precision

Instruments, WPI, FL, USA) or Midgard Current Source (Stoelting). Injection parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Forebrain regions were targeted following the stereotaxic coordinates of Paxinos and Franklin (2012) atlas. To target the Gracilis (Gr) and Cuneatus (Cu) nuclei, the head was secured in ventroflexed position. After a skin incision, the muscles of the back of the neck were dissected laterally from the midline, and the atlantooccipital membrane was opened to expose the dorsum of the lower medulla. The micropipette was inserted in Gr or Cu (between 0.2 and 0.5 mm caudal to the obex). To inject BDA in the spinal cord, a midline skin incision was made over the upper thoracic vertebrae. The paravertebral muscles were separated and retracted, the ligamenta flava incised and the micropipette tip was lowered into the spinal cord. After injections, micropipettes were left in place for 10 min before removal and wound closure.

(-----(*Insert Table 1 about here*)-----)

Tissue fixation and histological procedures

Animals were allowed to survive for 7 days, and were then perfused transcardially with 30 ml of saline, followed by 100 ml of 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA; diluted in 0.1 M PB, pH 7.4). Brains were then removed from the skull and postfixed overnight at 4°C in the same solution, and cryoprotected by embedding in 30% sucrose in 0.1 M PB, at 4°C, for 48 hrs. In retrograde transport experiments, the whole spinal cord was extracted and processed likewise.

In the retrograde fluorescent labeling experiments, three parallel series of 50 µm-thick coronal sections of the forebrain, brainstem and spinal cord were obtained on a freezing microtome (SM 2400; Leica, Germany). One series was mounted onto gelatin-coated glass slides, air dried, dehydrated in graded ethanol, defatted in xylene and coverslipped with DePex (Serva, Heidelberg, Germany). These sections were analyzed under an epifluorescence light microscope (Eclipse 600; Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) for retrograde labeling analysis. The second series was histochemically stained for cytochrome oxidase activity (CyO) (Wong-Riley et al., 1978) to help cytoarchitectonic localization of the labeling. The third series was stored at -20 °C.

In the BDA axonal labeling experiments, brains were freeze-sectioned in the coronal plane at 60 µm, and sections were collected in two parallel series. In the first, after peroxidase activity blocking by incubation in H₂O₂ 0.66 % (w/vol.) in 0.1M PB for 15

min, sections were incubated for 2 hrs. in avidin-biotin-peroxidase (1:100; Vectastain Elite™, Vector Laboratories, Burlingame, CA, USA) diluted in 0.1M PB. After washing, peroxidase was visualized using the glucose oxidase-3-3'diaminobenzidine (DAB; Sigma Aldrich) nickel sulfate-enhanced method (Shu et al., 1988). These sections were then counterstained with CyO histochemistry (Wong-Riley et al., 1978) for cytoarchitectonic localization of the labeling. Sections were finally mounted and coverslipped as above. A second series was used either for immunohistochemical processing as explained below or were kept in antifreeze solution at -20 °C for future analysis.

(-----(*Insert Table 2 about here*)-----)

Immunolabeling

All antibodies used in this study are commercially available and their host species, manufacturer, and dilutions are indicated in Table 2. Immunohistochemistry against vesicular glutamate transporter type 1 (vGLUT1), type 2 (vGLUT2) or gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) was performed in some brains. Following peroxidase activity blockage, sections were serially incubated in: a) 2 % Triton X-100® (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) + 5 % normal goat serum (NGS) + 1 % bovine serum albumin (BSA) in 0.1 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at room temperature (RT) for 2 hrs.; b) guinea pig anti-vGLUT1, guinea pig anti-vGLUT2 or rabbit anti-GABA polyclonal antibodies (Table 2), 2 % Triton X-100, 5 % NGS and 1 % BSA in 0.1M PBS with at 4 °C for 48 hrs.; c) biotinylated goat anti-guinea pig or goat anti-rabbit IgG, 2 % Triton X-100, 5 % NGS in 0.1M PBS at RT for 2 hrs.; d) in ABC Elite (Vector Laboratories) 1:100 in 0.1M PBS containing 2 % Triton X-100 at RT for 2 hrs. Multiple PBS rinses were intercalated between the above solutions. Finally, peroxidase activity was made visible using the glucose oxidase-diaminobenzidine method (Shu et al., 1988). In experiments involving immunolabeling against GABA, sections were pre-treated for antigen retrieval in sodium borohydride 1 % (w/vol.) for 30 min, RT.

For some experiments, simple or double immunofluorescence labeling was performed, in different combinations. The following antibodies were applied (Table 2): guinea pig anti-vGLUT2, rabbit anti-biotin and two different rabbit anti-glutamate decarboxylase 65 & 67 (GAD65/67). Besides, in tissue sections from the Rbp4-

Cre:Ai14 brains, a rabbit anti-red fluorescent protein (RFP) antiserum that also reacts against tdTomato was used.

In experiments involving immunolabeling against GAD65/67, sections were pre-treated for antigen retrieval in sodium borohydride 1 % (w/vol.) for 30 min, RT. In all experiments, sections were incubated, free-floating, in 2 % Triton X-100® and 5 % NGS in PB 0.1 M, 2 hrs., RT, rinsed in PB, and subsequently incubated in the pre-incubation solution plus the primary antibodies listed above (72 hrs., 4°C). Following multiple rinses, sections were then incubated in the corresponding secondary AlexaFluor-conjugated antibody (Table 2) in PB 0.1 M containing 2 % Triton X-100 and 5 % NGS; 2 hrs., RT.

After rinsing in PB 0.1 M, sections were finally mounted onto gelatin-coated glass slides, air dried, dehydrated in graded ethanol, defatted in xylene and coverslipped with DePex (Serva).

Retrograde labelling analysis

Retrograde tracer labeling was examined under an epifluorescence microscope Eclipse E600 (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) and mapped on JPEG images of the serial sections acquired with a Nikon DMA1200 digital camera and a motorized microscope stage (Proscan, Prior Scientific Instruments, Cambridge, UK) controlled by the Nis-Elements® BR 3.2 software (Nikon). Images were assembled into a single panoramic view using the Grab Large Image package of Nis-Elements® BR 3.2 software.

First, we analyzed the location in the thalamus of the tracer deposits. 40X images of all sections containing the tracer deposit (spaced 150 µm) were examined to delineate the deposit consistently. For each deposit, we outlined a core zone of solid, heavy fluorescence where no individual cell profiles were evident. Results suggest tracer uptake occurred mostly within this zone. Nevertheless, for a conservative interpretation of the labeling results, we also delineated and included in our analysis the peripheral halo of fainter fluorescence where individual labeled cell profiles were visible.

Retrograde tracer deposits were redrawn using the vectorial design software Canvas® X (ACD Systems, Victoria, Canada).

Retrogradely labeled cell somata were subsequently mapped across the brain and spinal cord. One out of six coronal tissue sections (~200 sections; 300 µm gap) was examined in each valid case. Autofluorescence images of the tissue sections were

acquired through 4x objective and the Nikon B2A filter cube (ex. 450–490) for anatomical reference. Regions containing labeled cells were imaged using a 10x objective and the Nikon UV2A filter cube (ex. 330–380).

Subsequently, retrogradely labeled somata were counted using Canvas X software tools. For each deposit, the fraction represented by the cells labeled in a particular structure over the total of labeled neurons was calculated. It should be emphasized that, given the many variables involved in the effectivity of retrograde transport labeling (Schofield et al., 2007), labeled cell counts were intended here only as an indirect approximation of the relative anatomical weight of the various sources of input to the thalamic nuclei under investigation.

As a visual aid for comparison of the spatial distribution patterns of corticothalamic neurons in the tangential dimension of the cerebral cortex, labeled cell somata were plotted on standard flat cortex maps registered to stereotaxic coronal levels (Figure 1a). We built this map from Franklin and Paxinos (2012) coronal diagrams. For each section, arc segments between cytoarchitectonic area borders measured on the section diagrams were plotted along a line. The lines were then stacked in order and aligned along the dorsal midline of the hemisphere (Figure 1). Additional details were derived from cytochrome-oxidase-stained brain sections. In the present study, the position in each section of the labeled corticothalamic cells was radially projected on the pial surface and plotted along its matching level line.

(-----(*Insert Figure 1 about here*)-----)

Anterograde BDA labeling analysis

For BDA-labelled experiments, sections were systematically examined under brightfield optics. Sections containing the BDA deposit were imaged and nuclear boundaries were delineated following cytoarchitectonic references provided by CyO counterstain.

BDA-labeled axons terminals in the thalamus were analyzed and imaged using 10-40X objectives. Axon arborizations were labeled in Golgi-like detail and showed frequent varicose swellings. Since axonal varicosities have been shown to contain presynaptic organelles and their overall size correlates with the number and/or strength of synapses they establish (Rovo et al., 2012; Groh et al., 2014; Rodriguez-Moreno et al., 2020), we decided to measure and compare labeled axon varicosity sizes. For this

purpose, varicosities were identified as such when their diameter was at least twice that of the adjacent axonal segments. As a proxy of bouton size measured on two-dimensional light microscope images, the major perimeter of each varicosity was focused in the Z axis at 100X and delineated, and its cross-sectional (maximal projection) area measured using the polyline and polygon tools of the Nis-Elements® BR 3.2 software (Nikon). Varicosities with cross-section area below the microscope resolution limit ($< 0.2 \mu\text{m}^2$) were not included in the analysis. For each glutamatergic labeled projection system, 100 randomly selected varicosities were measured, and 200 in the case of inhibitory system (total of 2200 varicosities). Varicosity size data for corticothalamic axons (Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018) are included here for direct comparison with other sources of input to the thalamus.

The location and distribution of the BDA-labeled varicosities in Po were plotted using a motorized Nikon Eclipse 80i microscope with 40-60X brightfield objectives, NeuroLucida controller, camera and software (v. 2020; MBF Bioscience, Williston, VT, USA). The CyO counterstain was used for thalamic nuclei delineation. In each section, all BDA-labeled varicosities were plotted using markers of NeuroLucida software.

Confocal microscope analysis

Immunofluorescence analyses of axon terminals were carried using a Spectral Leica TCS SP5 confocal microscope by sequentially applying argon (488 nm), diode-pumped solid-state (561 nm) and/or helium–neon (633 nm) laser lines to ensure complete channel separation. Regions of interest were imaged using 10x objective. In addition, images of BDA-labeled axons were taken also using 20X (plus 3x digital zoom) and 40X objectives. For each region of interest, 10 image stacks were obtained moving the sample in the Z-axis. Both image stacks and maximal projections were analyzed in separate and merged channels.

Experimental design and statistical analysis

Very small deposits of retrograde tracers often fail to label afferent pathways in consistent fashion. For this reason, out of a total of fifty-two retrograde tracer injections, we selected for analysis only eight injection experiments (6 injections Po and 2 in VPM) with deposits confined to the nuclei of interest and robust retrograde labeling in distant brain regions. Retrograde labeling produced by each deposit was thus analyzed

separately, as a n=1 experiment class.

From the BDA-labeling experiments, we analyzed only those in which the tracer deposit was confined to the intended target structure (43 injections). Comparison of varicosity mean cross-sectional areas was performed using one-way ANOVA analysis of variance plus T3 Dunnet's multiple comparisons as a post hoc test to identify significant interactions. Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-S) was used to compare size distributions of varicosities between different structures. Statistical analysis was computed using GraphPad Prism 5 software (San Diego, CA, USA) or SPSS Statistics software (v. 24; IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The threshold level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$, indicating this as (*), $p < 0.01$ as (**), and $p < 0.001$ as (***)

Results

(-----(*Insert Figure 2 about here*)-----)

Distribution within Po of vesicular glutamate transporter-specific immunolabeled axon terminals

To compare the general distribution within Po of glutamatergic axon terminals from the cerebral cortex with those of subcortical origin, we immunostained adjacent tissue sections against either vesicular glutamate transporters type 1 (vGLUT1) or type 2 (vGLUT2; Figure 2). The vGLUT1 protein is a well-established marker of the presynaptic vesicle pools in corticothalamic terminals. In contrast, vGLUT2 protein is present in glutamatergic brainstem and spinal presynaptic terminals, but absent from corticothalamic terminals (Fujiyama et al., 2001; Oliveira et al., 2003; Bopp et al., 2017). Although most thalamic projection neurons express vGLUT2 mRNA, their protein product is selectively directed to their axon terminals, outside the dorsal thalamus (Freneau et al., 2001; Fujiyama et al., 2001).

Immunostaining for vGLUT1 produced heavy punctate neuropil labeling across Po (Figure 2a and 2b). These puncta delineated, as empty spaces, cell body contours (Figure 2a1). In contrast, immunolabeling for vGLUT2 was markedly less dense overall than in the adjacent nuclei and was distributed in a variegated pattern. An extensive ventral and central portion of the nucleus contained only very small, spherical and weakly vGLUT2 labeled puncta. In contrast, an elongated patch in the dorsal portion of the nucleus, and smaller clusters along the border with the ventral posteromedial nucleus (VPM) contained heavily stained and larger puncta (Figure 2c-f), similar to those present in massive numbers in the adjacent VPM (Figure 2d2). The distribution and shape of these large vGLUT2 puncta-rich Po domains was consistent across animals.

(-----(*Insert Figure 3 about here*)-----)

Distribution of L5b corticothalamic axon terminals within Po

The vGLUT2 immunolabeling pattern revealed that subcortical excitatory afferent systems to Po concentrate selectively in some nucleus subdomains but are scant in others. In contrast, as both L5 and L6 corticothalamic terminals contain vGLUT1, the heavy immunolabeling precluded a reliable identification of L5 corticothalamic

terminals. To obtain an unobstructed view of these terminals, we examined the thalamus of transgenic mice Rbp4-Cre;Ai14. In these animals, most L5b neurons in the dorsolateral cerebral hemisphere constitutively express high levels of the fluorescent protein tdTomato (Hayashi et al., 2021). The thalamus of Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 animals showed a profuse plexus of tdTomato-labeled varicose terminal branches and boutons in Po. However, labeled branches were noticeably less dense or absent in some small dorsal and caudal Po domains (Figure 3a-d). Caudoventral Po contained a few isolated fluorescent cell bodies. In addition to Po, the lateral posterior nucleus received abundant labeled arborizations; in contrast, arborizations were virtually absent from VPM and the intralaminar nuclei.

A double-fluorescence analysis on Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 thalamus sections immunolabeled against vGLUT2 using fluorescein-tagged secondary antibodies revealed that the distribution within Po of the large glutamatergic subcortical terminals is complementary to that of the L5 corticothalamic terminals (Figure 3e-j). Meanwhile, regions containing small glutamatergic subcortical terminals can overlap to a variable extent with the L5 terminals. Overall, the dataset suggests a complex mosaic where descending L5 inputs and glutamatergic spinal/brainstem inputs can converge or remain segregated in variable proportions.

(-----(*Insert Figures 4 and 5 about here*)-----)

Distribution within Po of GABAergic axon terminals

Local interneurons are essentially absent from mouse Po (Evangelio et al., 2018; Jager et al., 2021), but the nucleus receives extrinsic GABAergic input from TRN, ZI (Bartho et al., 2002), and the APT (Bokor et al., 2005). To determine if these inhibitory pathways innervate Po in non-homogenous fashion, we immunolabeled Po sections with antibodies against the GAD65/67 isoforms, the enzymes for GABA synthesis (Erlander and Tobin, 1991; Figure 4). GAD65 is localized in synaptic vesicle pools of GABAergic neuron axons, whereas GAD67 is found in the cell bodies and proximal dendrites as well as in many axon terminals (Esclapez et al., 1994).

Within Po, the GAD65/67 labeling was limited to neuropil and consisted of two types of immunopositive puncta. Small ($<1 \mu\text{m}^2$) round and faintly labeled puncta were found throughout the nucleus (Figure 4l). In addition, several separate focal clusters of larger immunopositive puncta ($1-4 \mu\text{m}^2$), were also present (see arrowheads in Figure 4a-i). These clusters were more frequent and spread in the rostral portion of Po, and

became limited to the dorsal third of the nucleus at more caudal levels. Additional smaller groups of large puncta were also present along the border with VPM (Figure 4a-c). Immunolabeling in the adjacent VPM was much heavier overall. Inspection at high magnification, revealed that the VPM labeling consisted also of large puncta (Figure 4j). Immunolabeling with antibodies against GABA itself produced results consistent with the GAD65/67 pattern just described (Extended Figure 4-1).

Convergence/divergence of GABAergic terminals with glutamatergic terminals of subcortical origin or cortical L5 terminals

To analyze in detail the spatial relationships between GAD65/67-positive GABAergic terminals and vGLUT2-positive subcortical glutamatergic terminals, we conducted a double immunolabeling analysis for these markers on the same tissue sections (Figure 4d-i). We observed that the Po domains rich in large vGLUT2 terminals overlap to a large extent with the GAD65/67 large puncta clusters (Figure 4g-1). Despite close intermingling, puncta immunolabeled with each marker are always distinct (Figure 4p-r). In contrast, in the central and ventral portions of Po lacking large puncta clusters the overall distribution of each marker is less specific (Figure 4r), although vGLUT2 terminals tend to be more abundant in medial Po regions, while of GAD65/67 terminals are more densely packed in the lateral part of the nucleus.

The double-labeling analysis thus revealed that the Po microdomains that receive robust glutamatergic input of brainstem/spinal cord origin are also the preferential target of the large GABAergic terminals.

We subsequently compared the distribution within Po of the large GABAergic puncta with that of L5 boutons. To this end, we immunolabeled Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 mice thalamus tissue with GAD65/67 antibodies (Figure 5). This experiment revealed that the boutons of L5 pyramidal cell axons preferentially target the portions of Po that contain only very small GAD 65/67 puncta and avoid the domains where large GAD65/67 terminals are clustered.

Immunolabeling against vGLUT2 and GAD 65/67 on the same Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 tissue sections provided a direct visualization of the complex patterns of convergence/segregation within Po of inputs from cortical L5, the brainstem and spinal cord, or GABAergic nuclei (Figure 5). Overall, the immunolabeling patterns reveal a widespread innervation of Po by L5 terminals, with some small domains where subcortical

glutamatergic driver inputs prevail. GABA boutons are ubiquitous; however, they often accumulate and/or show larger sizes in domains containing large subcortical glutamatergic terminals.

(-----(*Insert Figure 6 about here*)-----)

Brain-wide retrograde tracer mapping of inputs to Po

While the immunofluorescence analysis revealed that excitatory and inhibitory inputs distribute unevenly within Po, it left unresolved the precise origin and local prevalence of the various afferent pathways. To this end, we microinjected retrograde tracers unilaterally into Po (Figure 6) and mapped the labeled cell somata across the whole brain and spinal cord. We specifically chose FG and FB because of their high sensitivity and reliable delineation of injection sites. In our experiments, the tracer deposits consisted of a core of continuously bright fluorescence with no discernible cellular elements in it. This core ranged in diameter between 250–450 μm . We presume that this is the region from which most or all tracer uptake and transport occurred. Deposits with a core under 200 μm of diameter failed to produce consistent labeling, or did not produce retrograde labeling at all. For about further 200 μm around this core, there was a fading halo of faint fluorescence where discrete cellular elements were recognizable. This halo probably made minimal, if any, contribution to the observed labeling (Schofield et al., 2007).

Six cases with FG or FB deposits limited to Po were considered valid for analysis (Figure 6a). Together, they covered about two-thirds of the nucleus. For comparison, we also analyzed the labeling produced by two further deposits in the adjacent VPM, a first-order relay nucleus (Figure 6b). We reconstructed the extent of each deposit on serial sections. Some deposits were completely separate (e.g.: cases Po1 vs. Po5 or Po6), while others overlap to variable extent.

(-----(*Insert Figures 7 and 8 about here*)-----)

Retrograde tracer mapping of corticothalamic inputs

Retrograde tracer injections in Po or VPM labeled massive numbers of corticothalamic cells (Figure 7a-b). In register with previous reports (Deschenes et al., 1998; Killackey and Sherman, 2003), neurons labeled in primary somatosensory area

(S1) after Po or VPM injections distributed in complementary laminar patterns. The Po injections labeled cells in layers 6b and 5b, while VPM injections labeled cells in L6a, with few additional cells in L6b (Figure 7e). In addition, there were notable disparities in the tangential spread across cortical areas (Figures 7 and 8; see also a summary in Extended Figure 8-1). VPM injections labeled corticothalamic neurons almost exclusively in ipsilateral S1 (Figure 7f), while Po injections invariably labeled cells in several cortical areas such as motor area (M1) and somatosensory areas S1 and S2. Additional cells were labeled by some Po injections in motor area M2, and/or in the ectorhinal, insular and perirhinal areas (Figures 7g and 8).

Injections in different Po regions produced specific patterns of labeling across areas. L6b cells were labeled in large numbers across the motor and somatosensory areas. Additional L6b cells were labeled in nearby areas, as well as in the contralateral hemisphere. L6a cells were labeled in large numbers always in M1, and often in area S2. In contrast, labeling of L6a neurons in area S1 was less abundant, except in those deposit located in rostral portions of the nucleus (Po1, Po2 and Po3; Figures 7 and 8).

Cells were labeled in L5b only in the ipsilateral hemisphere, mainly in S1, and often in S2 and M1. There was somatotopic order in this projection; cells were labeled in the macrovibrissae domain (cases Po1, Po2), snout domain (Po3), limbs domain (Po4, Po6) or trunk domain of S1 (Po5, Po6) in register with the position of each deposit and the known somatotopic organization of cell responses within Po (Diamond et al., 1992) (Figure 8b). Interestingly, the deposit in case Po5, which was centered approximately in the location of the vGLUT2 rich dorsal domain of Po (Figure 3d) showed an unusually low number of labeled L5b cells.

(-----*(Insert Figures 9 and 10 about here)*-----)

Retrograde tracer mapping of subcortical inputs

In addition to corticothalamic neurons, tracer deposits in Po labeled cell populations across the diencephalon, brainstem, and spinal cord (Figures 9 and 10). Sizable numbers of retrogradely labeled neurons were always found in some structures known to use GABA in their projections to the thalamus such as the TRN (Figure 9a), ZI (Figure 9b) and the APT (Figure 9c). In addition, labeled neurons were consistently found, in variable numbers, in subcortical regions known to use mainly glutamate in their

excitatory projections to thalamus, such as the SC intermediate layers (Figure 9d), the trigeminal complex (Figure 9e-g) and the DCN (Figure 9h). In some experiments, cells were labeled in the parabrachial complex (PB), the contralateral medial vestibular nucleus and some nuclei of the brainstem reticular formation, as well as in layers I-II, V and the lateral spinal nucleus of the spinal cord (Figure 9i).

In contrast, the subcortical neurons labeled by the VPM injections (which were both placed in the vibrissal domain of this nucleus) were present only in the trigeminal complex (principal and spinal interpolaris nuclei) and TRN (Figure 10). Overall, the contrasting patterns of labeling after either Po or VPM deposits are in register with the notion that while VPM neurons are devoted specifically to the relay of excitatory tactile signals from the face and mouth, the Po cells may integrate, along with cortical inputs from L5, diverse combinations of full-body tactile, motor, nociceptive, and attention-related signals conveyed via excitatory or inhibitory synapses (Yu et al., 2006; Groh et al., 2014; Ahissar and Oram, 2015).

Comparison between deposits that involved different Po regions reveal local fluctuations in the prevalence of the various afferent systems (Figure 10). For example, the deposits in the dorsal and caudal portions of the nucleus (Po4, Po5, Po6) labeled sizable numbers of cells in SC, while deposits involving ventral and anterior injections did not. Likewise, spinal cord and DCN cells were labeled in abundance only by dorsally and medially situated deposits, whereas cells in the principal trigeminal nucleus were labeled selectively by deposits near the border with VPM. Labeling in APT was robust in all cases except one limited to the ventral and central portions of the nucleus (case Po3). ZI input was substantial in all cases, but more prominent in dorso-caudal deposits (Po5 and Po6). In contrast, labeling in the TRN was robust in all cases. Cells were labeled in the substantia nigra reticulata only in cases Po3 and Po6.

(-----(*Insert Figure 11 about here*)-----)

Distribution within Po of afferent pathways

Retrograde tracing experiments informed about the sources and relative weight of the various input pathways to Po but did not delineate with precision the domains targeted or spared by each pathway. To this end, first we compared the fluorescent protein axonal labeling produced in Po by relatively large viral-vector injections placed in the

structures identified in the retrograde study (Figure 11; Allen Brain Connectome Dataset, 2011; Oh et al., 2014; Harris et al., 2019).

This analysis provided several important insights. First, it showed that APT axons arborize heavily in the most rostral Po levels (at about ~AP -1.50), but far less so at more caudal levels, where they concentrate mainly in the dorsolateral corner of the nucleus (Figure 11a-b). Remarkably, the dense APT terminal axon arborizations do not spread to other nuclei and display an uneven, clustered pattern. Second, viral vector injections in ZI consistently labeled axons targeting only the dorsal half of Po. Unlike APT, the ZI axon arborizations extend to the nearby laterodorsal and lateral posterior nucleus (Figure 11c-d). Vector injections in the spinal trigeminal nucleus label axons in ventral and lateral portions of Po and substantially more profuse axon arborizations in VPM (Figure 11e-f). Finally, axons from the intermediate/deep layers of the SC innervate only a dorsal fringe of Po but arborize densely in the adjacent lateral posterior nucleus (Figure 11g-h).

(-----(*Insert Figure 12 and 13 about here*)-----)

To analyze the fine morphology of axon arborizations and complete the delineation of their target territories, we made BDA microinjections in the various subcortical structures that innervate Po (Figure 12 and Extended Figure 12-1). Some BDA injections were placed in the same structures labeled in the Allen Brain Connectome dataset (2011). The distribution within Po of these BDA-labeled axon terminals was consistent with the viral transfection data and added topographic detail (Figure 13 and Extended Figure 13-1). Moreover, double fluorescence labeling for vGLUT2 and BDA confirmed that the projections from both the gracilis and cuneatus nuclei (n=5) target in focused manner the isolated vGLUT2-rich domain in the central and dorsal portion of Po and leave there large boutons immunopositive for this transporter (Figure 12a-d). Likewise, boutons labeled from BDA injections in the principal (n=4) and spinal trigeminal nuclei (n=8) were immunopositive for vGLUT2 and formed small clusters in the lateral border of the nucleus, near VPM (Figure 12e-h).

Vector transfection datasets did not include experiments involving the spinal cord. We examined the labeling produced in Po by large BDA injections (n=2) in the central spinal gray matter laminae at about the third cervical level and found labeled axons in the dorsomedial portion of Po (Extended figure 12-1 and Figure 13e) a region matching

that reported to respond to tactile stimulation of the limbs and trunk (Diamond et al., 1992).

(-----(*Insert Figure 14 about here*)-----)

Small deposits in different portions of the TRN (n=4), labeled richly branched and relatively focal arborizations in Po. The position of these arborizations varied in register with that of the TRN injections. For example, a BDA deposit in a central domain of TRN labeled axonal arborizations in dorsolateral Po, along the border with VPM, while a deposit in a ventral domain of TRN labeled axons only in the ventral region of Po (Figure 14). The distribution of APT and ZI BDA-labeled axon terminals within Po was consistent with the viral transfection data (Extended figure 14-1).

Overall, the labeled axon arborization patterns in the viral vector tracing datasets or BDA microinjections are consistent with the immunolabeling and retrograde tracing mapping results. Together, they delineate several subdomains within Po, each containing a specific combination of two or more overlapping excitatory (L5, DCN, trigeminal, SC) or inhibitory (APT, ZI) long-range input systems. These diverse input combinations might thus impinge on some Po projection neurons (Groh et al., 2014) while not on others. In contrast, the glutamatergic corticothalamic L6 terminals and GABAergic TRN terminals appear to cover Po homogeneously and in rough topographic fashion; hence, they probably reach all Po neurons with similar prevalence.

(-----(*Insert Figure 15 about here*)-----)

Axonal varicosity sizes of the input pathways

In most axon terminals, the size of varicosities reflects accumulations of mitochondria and synaptic vesicle pools at presynaptic sites (which may be single or multiple). Hence, varicosity size provides an indirect indication of important functional parameters such as synapse release probability and strength (Sherman and Guillery, 2002; Rodriguez-Moreno et al., 2020). Interestingly, some of the afferent inputs to Po investigated in the present study such as the glutamatergic L5b corticothalamic (Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018) or the GABAergic ZI and APT axons (Halassa and Acsady, 2016) had been previously shown to have unusually large varicosities in their terminal axon branches.

To compare in systematic fashion varicosity sizes across the various input systems targeting Po and as an indirect indication of their synaptic strength, we measured their maximal projection areas in axons labeled by BDA injections in different subcortical structures (Figure 12 and Extended figure 12). For comparison, we included in this analysis a previously published dataset of bouton sizes from BDA deposits located in L5b, L6a and L6b (Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2018).

First, we compared the axonal varicosities from cortical and subcortical glutamatergic structures (Figure 15). For each structure, we analyzed both the frequency of size distribution (Figure 15e) and the mean size (Figure 15f). Statistical data comparisons are summarized in Extended Table 15-1. We found that the mean sizes of varicosities in axons originated in from L6a and L6b S1BF were always significantly smaller than those originated in subcortical structures or L5b ($0.60 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $0.58 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}^2$, respectively; T3 Dunnet's, $p < 0.05$) and had a significantly different frequency in size distribution (K-S, $p < 0.001$ for all comparisons). The varicosities from nucleus gracilis, cuneatus, ventrolateral region of the principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-VL) and SpVI, as well as the deep intermediate layers of the SC did not differ significantly in size from cortical L5b varicosities ($2.42 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{m}^2$). The varicosities in the caudal portion of the spinal trigeminal nuclei (SpVC) were significantly bigger than those from L5b ($4.16 \pm 0.34 \mu\text{m}^2$; T3 Dunnet's, $p = 0.003$). Other glutamatergic axons had significantly smaller axonal varicosities than cortical L5b, including some trigeminal subnuclei (SpVO, PrV-DM), PB and axons from the central laminae of the spinal cord.

(-----(*Insert Figure 16 about here*)-----)

Varicosity sizes were likewise measured and compared among GABAergic axon populations (Figure 16), analyzing the frequency of size distribution (Figure 16e) and the mean size (Figure 16f). We included in this analysis the varicosities from TRN axons in VPM. Statistical data are summarized in Extended Table 16-1. The analysis revealed that the largest varicosities are those arising from APT ($1.96 \pm 0.09 \mu\text{m}^2$) and ZI ($1.80 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{m}^2$). No significant differences were found between these populations (Figure 16f). Axonal varicosities in TRN axons across most of Po were significantly smaller ($0.84 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}^2$; T3 Dunnet's, $p < 0.001$ for all comparisons) and had a significantly different frequency in size distribution (K-S, $p < 0.001$). In contrast, the

terminals from this nucleus were much larger along the lateral border of Po, near VPM ($1.83 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{m}^2$) as well as inside VPM ($1.58 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{m}^2$, T3 Dunnet's, $p < 0.001$).

Quantitative estimation of local input convergence

As a way to gauge the convergence of different inputs, we compared the numbers of cells labeled in the various structures in each retrograde tracing experiment. We counted cells in the whole brain and spinal cord. To normalize for fluctuations in labeling efficacy or injection volume between experiments, cells in each structure were compared as percentages over labeled neuron totals. This parameter, often referred to as Fraction of Labeled Neurons (FLN; Markov et al., 2011) provides an objective comparison of the relative anatomical weight of the pathways. Note, however, that FLN cannot be directly equated to functional impact without factoring in other parameters such as the local convergence and strength of the synapses, as well as the postsynaptic receptor mechanisms involved (Sherman and Guillery, 2002; Rodriguez-Moreno et al., 2020).

(-----(*Insert Figure 17 about here*)-----)

Numbers of neurons involved in the excitatory afferent systems

First, we compared the relative contributions of the various glutamatergic input pathways to the Po regions impregnated in each retrograde tracer experiment. We considered this analysis relevant because the ratio of cortical vs. subcortical origins of excitatory inputs is widely used for functional classification of thalamic nuclei. According to this classification, FO are the thalamic nuclei that relay to the cortex ascending excitatory signals from the subcortical systems, while HO nuclei send back to cortex signals received from the cortex via collaterals of L5 axons. A third “integrator” category has been proposed for nuclei like Po, where at least some neurons receive both L5 and excitatory subcortical inputs, and can integrate them in complex nonlinear fashion (Groh et al., 2014).

Among the excitatory pathways we compared the numbers of cells labeled in pathways previously shown to drive Po neuron firing and specify their information content (hence referred to as “driver” pathways; Sherman and Guillery, 1996). We excluded corticothalamic L6 cells because we assume that their prevalence is homogeneous across Po, and their effect on thalamus cells essentially modulatory, fine-

tuning variables such as temporal profile of the “driver” signals carried by other pathways (Sherman, 2016; Briggs, 2020).

As a first step, we compared labeled cell numbers in cortical L5b vs. all glutamatergic subcortical structures (Figure 17b). In the VPM control cases, subcortical sensory afferents represented always over ~ 90 %. Such massive prevalence may even be an underestimate, as the labeled L5 cells probably represent passing axons directed to Po that were impregnated at the injection site. In contrast, in Po L5 cells prevailed (~ 65-75 %) in all cases except in two (24.7 % in case Po5 and 42.7 % in Po6) whose deposits overlapped the vGLUT2-rich domain in central-dorsal Po. Overall, these findings show that while most of Po is robustly innervated by L5, all parts the nucleus receive a sizable number of inputs from subcortical excitatory structures. The central and dorsal vGLUT2-rich domain of Po receives a proportion of subcortical excitatory inputs in a proportion nearing that of the “FO-relay” VPM.

Cortical L5b input to Po originated mainly from S1 (Figure 17d), finding at least 63% of L5b labelled cells in this area and up to 98.3% in case Po2. Others Po domains also receive a significant percentage of L5b inputs from other cortical areas, as the motor cortex (Po1, 16.5 %; Po5, 19.5 %) or S2 (Po3, 20.8 %).

The trigeminal complex was labeled in all cases, but most robustly in experiments placed in rostral and ventral levels of Po. This input arose always from the SpV (oralis and interpolaris nuclei present 12.3-29.3 % of subcortical cells), and, in the deposits injected in the anterior half of Po, also from PrV (Figure 17e). Cells in the intermediate layers of SC were most numerous in those with deposits in dorsal and caudal Po, being the majority (56 %) among the glutamatergic subcortical cells labeled in case Po6. Dorsal column nuclei cells were labeled in all cases, yet they were markedly more numerous when the deposit overlapped the position of the dorsal vGLUT2-rich domain of Po (30.6 % in Po4 and 21.6 % in Po5). Likewise, spinal cord neurons were a small but consistent fraction of the subcortical glutamatergic afferent mix. The most abundant labeling was observed in cases located in dorsomedial Po (up to 23.5 % in Po5 and Po6; Figure 17e).

Numbers of neurons involved in GABAergic afferent pathways

Likewise, we compared the proportion of retrogradely labeled cells within the group of structures known to innervate the thalamus via GABAergic axons (Figure 17c). TRN

was robustly labeled in all Po injection cases, although its prevalence among GABAergic inputs fluctuated widely (82.7-32.8 %) depending on the presence or absence of other inputs. Projections from APT were labeled after every retrograde tracer injection in Po. Their prevalence among other GABAergic inputs ranged from 8.0 % (case Po3, involving ventral Po) to 49.6 % (case Po4 involving dorsal-central Po). Neurons projecting to Po from the ZI were likewise labeled by every Po injection. They fluctuated between 5.6-29.7 %, and were most abundant after injections involving dorsal and caudal Po portions. Remarkably, we found a positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.75$) between the number of labeled cells in the extra-reticular inhibitory structures with the subcortical structures (Figure 17f), but not with number of L5b cells ($R^2 = 0.17$; Figure 17g). In striking contrast with Po, VPM received GABAergic inputs exclusively from TRN (Figure 17c).

(-----(*Insert Figure 18 about here*)-----)

Discussion

We mapped the origin and intranuclear distribution of the excitatory and inhibitory input pathways to Po, a representative HO nucleus of the mouse thalamus. Results reveal that while some pathways (L6, TRN) innervate all regions of Po with similar abundance, other pathways (L5, DCN, trigeminal, SC, spinal cord, APT, ZI) concentrate in some regions but are absent from others, creating within Po a complex mosaic of partly overlapping domains (Figure 18). Our observations are in register with the notion that the HO/associative nuclei are a place where variable combinations of disparate powerful inputs can be integrated by specific thalamic cell populations, giving rise to functionally diverse subnetworks.

Cortical inputs to Po

The cortex is the main source of inputs to Po. In consonance with the massive presence vGLUT1 terminals (Figure 2), which in the thalamus are almost exclusively of cortical origin (Graziano et al., 2008; Zhang et al., 2018), our retrograde tracer Po injections labeled invariably large numbers of pyramidal cortical cells in L6 and L5.

L6b corticothalamic pathways are by far the largest contingent of cells innervating Po. L6 cells consistently were labeled in areas S1 and S2, M1 and ectorhinal cortices, which, interestingly, are the regions that Po thalamocortical axons innervate (Ohno et al., 2012; Rodriguez-Moreno et al., 2020). A small but consistent number of L6b projections originate in the same areas of the contralateral hemisphere. In contrast, Po L6a inputs mainly from M1 and S2, an observation consistent with the notion that L6a inputs arise from those areas that Po innervates in *feedforward* laminar arborization patterns (L4-3) while L6b come mainly from those innervated in *feedback* (L5a and 1) pattern (Deschenes et al., 1998; Ohno et al., 2012; Casas-Torremocha et al., 2019). Despite sheer numbers, L6a and L6b corticothalamic pathways are regarded to be modulatory in function, as their main effect is to fine-tune variables of thalamic neuron firing (e.g.: temporal profile) while preserving its main information content (Sherman, 2016; Briggs, 2020).

In contrast, L5 corticothalamic inputs have been shown to drive the firing of the thalamic cells, determining the fundamental information content of their output (e.g.: receptive field); hence, they have been functionally classified to as “driver” pathways (Sherman and Guillery, 1996, 2006). In register with previous observations in rats (Bourassa et al., 1995; Veinante et al., 2000b; Alloway et al., 2003; Killackey and Sherman, 2003; Sumser et al., 2017), we show that L5b inputs to Po originate mainly from ipsilateral S1, with a clear topographic order. This order relates the position of the labeling in different S1 domains with the location of a tracer deposit in Po and the somatotopic map of cell responses within this nucleus (Diamond et al., 1992). An equivalent, but more coarse topographic ordering is detectable in the smaller contingents of L5b projections to Po from S2 and M1 (compare cases Po1 vs. Po6, or cases Po3 vs. Po6 in Figures 7 and 8).

The retrograde tracing experiments also show that convergence of L5b projections from two or three areas can occur in some Po zones (cases Po1, Po3, Po6; see Sampathkumar et al., 2021) but not in other Po zones that receive L5b input exclusively from area S1 (cases Po2, Po4; Figure 8). It is also of note that the L5b retrograde labeling was unusually scant in case Po5 (Figure 8b), akin to that observed after retrograde tracer injections in the FO nucleus VPM (Figure 7f). Case Po5 injection (Figure 6) matches the position of a vGLUT2-rich and Rbp4-Cre: Ai14 neuropil-poor domain located midway along the dorsal third of Po (Figure 3). Together these observations suggest that the centrodorsal Po domain may have a FO-like character (see discussion below).

Subcortical inputs to Po

Our data shows that Po receives sizable direct input connections from structures in the diencephalon, brainstem and spinal cord. These include both pathways known to use mainly excitatory neurotransmitters such as glutamate (DCN, trigeminal sensory complex, and SC) and pathways that use inhibitory neurotransmitters like GABA (TRN, APT, ZI). The labeling patterns observed with antibodies against vGLUT2, or GAD67/65 and GABA (Figures 2-5) reveal that some of these connections are very unevenly distributed within Po, both in terms of local abundance as well as of the morphology/size of the labeled puncta.

DCN and spinal cord inputs: We show that Po receives a relatively small but robust projection from the contralateral DCN. These fibers convey low-threshold, mechanoreceptive primary afferents encoding pressure/distortion and target mainly the ventroposterior lateral nucleus (Graziano et al., 2008). We observed that, in addition, DCN axons target the dorsal and central region of the nucleus, in a pattern equivalent to that described in rat Po (Lund and Webster, 1967; Villanueva et al., 1998; Uemura et al., 2020). In addition, we show that DCN axons form the large immunopositive boutons that abound in the vGLUT2-rich dorsal domain of Po, a finding in register with the fact that the DCN projection neurons express intense vGLUT2 mRNA signal (Hisano et al., 2002). The distribution of labeled axon varicosities after BDA injections limited to the Cu or Gr indicate that axons from the Cu nucleus terminate more dorsally and laterally within Po than those from nucleus Gr (Figure 13c-d).

We show that direct spinal inputs reach the dorsomedial portion of Po, and that they originate mainly in contralateral dorsal horn L1, and L4-7 at all levels of the spinal cord. These axons may thus transmit to Po nociceptive and cutaneous information from the neck, trunk and limbs. These spinothalamic axons are not directed exclusively to Po, as they arborize also in the adjacent intralaminar nuclei. Within Po, terminals are present only in the medial and dorsal region of Po and seem to be more abundant in the caudal half of the nucleus. The mean size of the spinothalamic varicosities and those of the spinal trigeminal nucleus axons is the same (Figure 15f). The spinothalamic projection neurons contain exclusively vGLUT2 mRNA (Person et al., 2006). It is thus possible that many of the large puncta present in the dorsomedial corner of Po represent spinothalamic axon terminals.

Trigeminal inputs: The trigeminothalamic pathways convey tactile (dynamic and static), thermal and nociceptive signals from head and orofacial regions. The main thalamic target of the trigeminal sensory complex axons is VPM, but many of these axons also extend branches into Po (Veinante and Deschenes, 1999; Pierret et al., 2000). Our retrograde and anterograde labeling data show that the trigeminal complex projections are present in ventral and central Po but very scant in the dorsomedial third of the nucleus. Studies in rats have shown that Po receives most of its ascending inputs from SpVI and that these axons form large varicosities (Veinante and Deschenes, 1999; Lavallee et al., 2005). Anterograde labeling experiments show that the trigeminal axons remain relatively scattered within ventral Po. This may explain why, although

trigemino-thalamic neurons mostly express vGLUT2 mRNA (Graziano et al., 2008; Ge et al., 2014), ventral Po shows only sparse vGLUT2 labeling. In contrast, trigeminal terminals mass into clusters of large vGLUT2 immunopositive boutons along the lateral border of Po (Figure 12e-g). Some trigeminal axon varicosities near the VPM border are the largest of all measured in our experiments (Figure 15). In register with their bouton morphology, trigeminal axons have been shown to drive Po cells with short latency, as typical driver inputs; however, their effect on Po cells is suppressed most of the time by the powerful GABAergic inputs from ZI and APT (Trageser and Keller, 2004; Lavallee et al., 2005; see below).

Superior colliculus inputs: Our data indicate that the intermediate layers of the SC innervate the dorsal third of Po, but not the ventral part of the nucleus. These SC layers receive sensory and motor functions, and many of them show multimodal responses (Stein et al., 1989). Colliculothalamic terminals in Po have not been functionally or ultrastructurally investigated, but in the adjacent lateral posterior nucleus they show the properties of “driver” pathways (Kelly et al., 2003; Wurtz et al., 2005; Bickford, 2015). It has been recently demonstrated that SC drives activity in Po neurons via a monosynaptic pathway (Gharraei et al., 2020).

Anterior pretectal nucleus inputs: APT is mainly involved in antinociception (Foster et al., 1989; Genaro and Prado, 2021) and is extensively connected, in addition to other structures, with pain and somatosensory related brainstem nuclei. In register with previous studies in rats (Bokor et al., 2005; Giber et al., 2008; Wanaverbecq et al., 2008), we show that APT axons are present across most of Po and leave dense clustered arborizations in the rostral region of the nucleus. The position of these arborizations aligns with a heavy concentration of large GAD65/67 puncta in this region. We observed a rough topography in this projection, with dorsal and rostral portions of APT innervating lateral portions of Po and ventral-caudal APT innervating anterior Po. Our data show that, although some APT axons may spread to surrounding nuclei (Bokor et al., 2005), this pathway is heavily focused on rostral Po. Boutons in APT axons are the largest among GABAergic Po inputs, but they are clearly smaller than those in the glutamatergic trigeminal, DCN and L5b axons (Figures 15f and 16f). The APT axon boutons contact the proximal dendrites of relay cells via multiple synapses and exert powerful and precise inhibitory control on thalamic activity (Bokor et al., 2005; Wanaverbecq et al., 2008).

Zona incerta inputs: The ZI shares many of its inputs and output sources with the APT and is reciprocally connected to it, as part of a synergistic network (Mitrofanis, 2005; Giber et al., 2008). In agreement with observations in rats, we show that ZI and APT converge on rostral Po, mainly in the dorsolateral zone of the nucleus rich in large GABA puncta (Figures 4-5) and more sparsely at caudal and ventral levels (Figure 11). Lavalley et al. (2005) emphasized that the effect of ZI inputs did not manifest in all Po neurons and was observed mainly in rostral and dorsolateral Po. The ZI boutons are as large as those of APT (Figure 17f), and likewise form multisynaptic GABAergic terminals on proximal dendrites, exerting a powerful tonic inhibition of a subpopulation of Po neurons (Trageser and Keller, 2004; Lavalley et al., 2005). Together, APT and ZI provide strong, focal and temporally precise inhibition, that impacts the timing of individual spikes and therefore, the content of the thalamic signals (Halassa and Acsady, 2016).

Thalamic reticular nucleus inputs: TRN inputs to thalamus regulate gain control and rhythm genesis, modulating the rate of thalamic projection neurons spike trains, while preserving their information content. These effects can be gradual and are exerted on relatively large cell populations, such as individual nuclei (Halassa and Acsady, 2016). Every region of Po and VPM is innervated by GABAergic TRN axons. The richly arborized and topographic TRN axons (Pinault et al., 1995) are probably the main contributor to the fine-grained, ubiquitous neuropil immunostaining for markers of GABA terminals in Po (Figure 4). In contrast, the clusters of large GAD65/67 puncta observed in the rostral and dorsal regions of Po are related to the APT and ZI terminals. Despite the fact that VPM receives GABAergic inputs exclusively from TRN, the overall GABA neuropil labeling is weaker in Po than in VPM. This may reflect the fact that the TRN axons innervating Po show three times less varicosity frequency than those targeting VPM (Pinault and Deschenes, 1998). We find it remarkable that TRN boutons in VPM and the lateral border of Po display significantly larger varicosities than TRN axons in the rest of Po (Figure 16f). Is unclear if they are branches from TRN axon targeting VPM or a specific TRN subpopulation (Lam and Sherman, 2007; Halassa et al., 2014; Crabtree, 2018; Li et al., 2020).

Input microdomains in HO nuclei

The image of the Po neuropil that emerges from the combined evidence presented in this study is that of a complex mosaic of segregated but partly overlapping domains (Figure 18). This pattern is directly visualized, to some extent, in the fluorescence overlays of multilabeling for GABAergic, L5 and vGLUT2 terminals (Figure 5).

It must be noted, however, that such heterogeneity is present in most, but not all, the Po inputs. For example, two numerically robust inputs (L6 and TRN) seem to be distributed across the nucleus in evenly fashion. Intriguingly, although they use different neurotransmitters, these two pathways share some key features: their axon arborizations are profuse and relatively widespread, they target distal dendrites with small boutons and they have only modulatory effects on thalamic cell firing. In contrast, the remaining pathways (L5, DCN, trigeminal, spinal, SC, APT, or ZI) have a more focal distribution, targeting only some Po regions and establish relatively large synaptic terminals that, as far as it is known, are located on proximal dendrites. As discussed earlier, each of these pathways are powerful enough to determine with high temporal acuity (in excitatory or inhibitory fashion) cell spike coding.

In view of the intermingled arrangement and small size of the neuropil domains, it is intriguing to consider that the Po neurons have bushy dendritic trees with a mean radius in mice of about 200-250 μm (Figure 18; see also Ohno et al., 2012). Given these constraints, it is likely that most Po cells, particularly those situated near domain borders, can simultaneously receive powerful inputs from two or more sources, in a variety of graded combinations. The mouse Po, and probably other associative/HO nuclei of the thalamus as well, might thus be a place for direct convergence and integration on the membrane of individual neurons, in combinatorial fashion, of powerful inputs (excitatory and/or inhibitory) originated in separate parts of the brain. There is already evidence that this integration can occur. L5 and trigeminal inputs synapsing onto the same Po neuron can be integrated in nonlinear, time dependent fashion and serve to detect coincident sensory and motor activity (Groh et al., 2014; Ahissar and Oram, 2015). Likewise, direct convergence onto single Po cells of L5 inputs from two separate cortical areas has been recently demonstrated (Sampathkumar et al., 2021). The emergent computations and specialized subnetworks made possible by association/HO nuclei might well be a driving force behind the remarkable expansion in relative size of these nuclei in some mammalian lineages, including ours.

Author Contributions

DCT, CP and FC designed the experiments,

ZM, AHS and SH provided Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 transgenic mice brains,

DCT and MRT performed the experiments,

DCT, MRT and CP analyzed the data,

DCT, MRT, CP and FC prepared the figures and tables,

DCT and FC wrote the paper with input from CP, MRT, AHS, SH, LP and ZM.

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Figures

Figure 1

Figure 2

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Figure 13

Figura 14

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 18

Table 1. Injection parameters applied to selectively inject BDA in brain regions that innervate Po.

Brain region	AP	ML	DV	Tip diameter (µm)	Current intensity (µA)	Time (min)	Cycle (s ON/OFF)
TRN	-1.5	±2.2	-3.0	5–7	0.2–0.3	40–45	1
ZI	-2.1	±1.5	-4.0	6–8	0.3–0.5	40–45	1
APT	-2.8	±1.1	-2.6	8–12	0.8–1	40–45	1
SC	-3.3	±1.0	-2.0	8–10	0.8–1	20–30	1
Gr	-0.2*	±0.5	-0.2*	15–20	1–2	20–30	7
Cu	-0.5*	±1.0	-0.2*	15–20	1–2	20–30	7
MVe	-5.8	±0.9	-3.0	10–15	1–2	30–40	7
PrV-VL	-5.4	±1.9	-3.7	10–15	1–2	30–40	7
PrV-DM	-5.4	±1.9	-3.2	10–15	1–2	30–40	7
SpVO	-5.8	±1.8	-3.7	10–15	0.8–1	30–40	1
SpVI	-7.2	±1.8	-3.0	10–15	0.8–1	30–40	1
SpVC	-7.7	±1.8	-2.7	10–15	0.8–1	30–40	1
Spinal cord	C1-C2	±0.5	-0.3	12–14	1.5–2	20–30	7

Table 1 legend: Injection parameters applied to selectively inject BDA in brain regions that innervate Po. Stereotaxic coordinates for the anteroposterior (AP), mediolateral (ML) and dorsoventral (DV) levels respect to Bregma are represented. Asterisks indicate distance to the obex. Abbreviations: TRN: Reticular prethalamic nucleus, ZI: Zona incerta. APT: Anterior pretectal nucleus; SC: Superior colliculus, middle & deep layers; Gr: Nucleus Gracilis; Cu: Nucleus cuneatus; MVe: Medial Vestibular nucleus; PrV-VL: Principal trigeminal nucleus, Ventrolateral portion; PrV-DM: Principal trigeminal nucleus, Dorsomedial portion; SpVO: Spinal Trigeminal nucleus, Oral division; SpVI: Spinal Trigeminal nucleus, interpolar division; SpVC: Spinal Trigeminal nucleus, caudal division.

Table 2. List of antibodies used in this study.

Antibodies	Manufacturer	Dilution
Guinea pig anti-vGLUT1 polyclonal antibody serum	Chemicon®, Merck Millipore. Cat. n°: AB5905	1:2000
Guinea pig anti-vGLUT2 polyclonal antibody serum	Sigma-Aldrich. Cat. n°: AB2251-I	1:2000
Biotinylated goat anti-guinea pig polyclonal IgG	Vector Laboratories. Cat. n°: BA-7000	1:200
Rabbit anti-biotin polyclonal antibody serum	Abcam. Cat. n°: AB53494	1:500
Rabbit anti-red fluorescent protein (RFP) polyclonal antibody serum	MBL International. Cat. n°: PM005	1:500
Rabbit anti-GABA	Sigma. Cat. n°: A2052	1:500
Rabbit anti-glutamate decarboxylase 65 & 67 (GAD65/67) polyclonal antibody serum	Chemicon®, Merck Millipore. Cat. n°: AB1511	1:100
Rabbit anti- GAD65/67 polyclonal antibody serum	Sigma-Aldrich. Cat. n°: ABN904	1:100
AlexaFluor® 488-conjugated goat anti-guinea pig polyclonal IgG	ThermoFisher. Cat. n°: A-11073	1:200
AlexaFluor® 568-conjugated goat anti-rabbit polyclonal IgG	ThermoFisher. Cat. n°: A-11011	1:200
AlexaFluor® 647-conjugated goat anti-rabbit polyclonal IgG	ThermoFisher. Cat. n°: A-21244	1:200

Table 2 legend: List of antibodies used in this study. For each antibody, manufacturer, catalogue number and dilution used are indicated.

Extended Figure 4-1

Extended Figure 8-1

Extended Figure 12-1

Extended Figure 13-1

Extended Figure 14-1

1 **Extended Table 15-1**

	Mean ± sd	Test	Gr													
Gr	2.50 ± 0.21	Anova K-S	- -													
				Cu												
Cu	3.04 ± 0.31	Anova K-S	1.000 0.261	- -												
					PrV-DM											
PrV-DM	1.42 ± 0.19	Anova K-S	0.016 * 0.000 ***	0.001 ** 0.000 ***	- -											
						PrV-VL (Center Po)										
PrV-VL (Center Po)	0.93 ± 0.08	Anova K-S	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.826 0.344	- -										
							PrV-VL (Border Po)									
PrV-VL (Border Po)	3.59 ± 0.31	Anova K-S	0.290 0.069	1.000 0.031 *	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	- -									
								SpVO								
SpVO	1.09 ± 0.08	Anova K-S	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	1.000 0.005 **	1.000 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	- -								
									SpVI							
SpVI	1.78 ± 0.14	Anova K-S	0.327 0.020 *	0.021 * 0.008 **	1.000 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.001 **	0.004 ** 0.000 ***	- -							
										SpVC						
SpVC	4.16 ± 0.34	Anova K-S	0.004 ** 0.000 ***	0.726 0.001 **	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	1.000 0.099	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	- -						
											SC					
SC	1.93 ± 0.15	Anova K-S	0.913 0.193	0.116 0.013 *	0.951 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.002 **	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	1.000 0.443	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	- -					
												Spinal cord				
Spinal cord	1.40 ± 0.13	Anova K-S	0.001 ** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	1.000 0.008 **	0.238 0.008 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.985 0.069	0.989 0.008 **	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.547 0.000 ***	- -				
													PB			
PB	1.23 ± 0.08	Anova K-S	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	1.000 0.005 **	0.571 0.005 **	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	1.000 0.020 *	0.066 0.069	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.005 ** 0.008 **	1.000 0.794	- -			
														L5b S1BF		
L5b S1BF	2.42 ± 0.23	Anova K-S	1.000 0.031 *	1.000 0.099	0.074 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.204 0.001 **	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.751 0.008 **	0.003 ** 0.000 ***	0.998 0.008 **	0.013* 0.000 ***	0.000*** 0.000 ***	- -		
															L6a S1BF	
L6a S1BF	0.60 ± 0.02	Anova K-S	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.005 ** 0.000 ***	0.014 * 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000*** 0.000 ***	0.000*** 0.000 ***	0.000*** 0.000 ***	- -	
																L6b S1BF
L6b S1BF	0.58 ± 0.03	Anova K-S	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.003 ** 0.000 ***	0.007 ** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000 *** 0.000 ***	0.000*** 0.000 ***	0.000*** 0.000 ***	0.000*** 0.000 ***	1.000 0.261	- -

2
3 **Extended Table 15-1.** Quantitative analysis of varicosity size from glutamatergic structures. Data from L5b, L6a and L6b were previously
4 published in Hoerder-Suabedissen et al., 2017.

	Mean ± sd	Test	ZI				
ZI	1.80 ± 0.08	Anova	-	APT			
		K-S	-				
APT	1.96 ± 0.09	Anova	0.997	-	Rt (center Po)		
		K-S	0.779	-			
TRN (center Po)	0.84 ± 0.03	Anova	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-	Rt (VPM)	
		K-S	0.000 ***	0.000 ***	-		
TRN (VPM)	1.58 ± 0.06	Anova	0.546	0.020 *	0.000 ***	-	Rt (border Po)
		K-S	0.052	0.027 *	0.000 ***	-	
TRN (border Po)	1.83 ± 0.06	Anova	1.000	0.999	0.000 ***	0.074	-
		K-S	0.010 *	0.014 *	0.000 ***	0.005 **	-

5
6 **Extended Table 16-1.** Quantitative analysis of varicosity size from GABAergic
7 structures. Comparison of varicosity mean cross-sectional areas was performed using
8 one-way ANOVA analysis of variance plus T3 Dunnet's multiple comparisons as a post
9 hoc test to identify significant interactions. Two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (K-
10 S) was used to compare size distributions of varicosities between different structures.
11

12

13

Figure legends

14

15 **Figure 1. Generation of an isometric surface map of mouse somatic motor and**
16 **sensory areas.**

17 (a, b) We use this map to represent and analyze retrograde cortical labeling in
18 subsequent figures. This map was created by aligning all the pial contours of Franklin
19 and Paxinos (2012) coronal section diagrams as parallel lines along the dorsal midline
20 “watershed” of the cerebral hemisphere (black arrowheads, and dashed black line on the
21 map). (c) Flat map detail of the areas used in the subsequent figures to represent the
22 corticothalamic labeling. Abbreviations: A1: Primary Auditory area; Cg: Cingulate
23 cortex; Ect: Ectorrinal area; FrA: Frontal Association; INS: Insular (granular +
24 dysgranular) cortex; M1: Primary Motor area; M2: Secondary Motor area; S1: Primary
25 Somatosensory area; S2: Secondary Somatosensory area; V1: Primary Visual area.

26

27 **Figure 2. Distribution within Po of vesicular glutamate transporter-specific**
28 **immunolabeled axon terminals.**

29 (a, b) Microphotographs showing in different coronal sections of Po the distribution of
30 terminals marked by immunohistochemistry against the glutamate vesicular transporter
31 type 1 (vGLUT1). High-magnification details detail in shown in a1. (c-f)
32 Microphotographs showing in different coronal sections of Po the distribution of
33 terminals marked by immunohistochemistry against the glutamate vesicular transporter
34 type 2 (vGLUT2). High-magnification details showing larger vGLUT2 terminals in
35 dorsal domains (d1) and in the border with the ventral posteromedial nucleus (VPM;
36 d2), smaller vGLUT2 terminals in the lateral portion of Po (d3) and domains with
37 almost absence of these terminals in the ventral portion (e1). Bregma coronal level (in
38 mm) is indicated on the upper right corner. Scale bars: a-f 250 μm ; a1, d1-d3 and e1 30
39 μm .

40

41 **Figure 3. Distribution of L5 corticothalamic and vGLUT2-positive axon terminals**
42 **within Po.**

43 Double immunofluorescence labelling against tdTomato and vGLUT2 were performed
44 in Rbp4-Cre;Ai14 mice. High-resolution confocal images showing in three different

45 coronal sections of Po the distribution of tdTomato (L5 axons; **a-d**; magenta), vGLUT2
46 (**e-g**; green), and its merge (**h-j**). Noted that the distribution within Po of the large
47 glutamatergic subcortical terminals is complementary to that of the L5 corticothalamic
48 terminals. High-magnification detail of L5 axonal varicosities in Po is shown in **b**.
49 Bregma coronal level (in mm) is indicated above. Scale bars: a, c-j 250 μ m; b 15 μ m.

50

51 **Figure 4. Distribution of glutamatergic subcortical and GABAergic axon terminals**
52 **within Po.**

53 High-resolution confocal images showing in different coronal sections of Po in
54 C57BL/6 mice the distribution of terminals labeled by immunohistochemistry against
55 glutamate decarboxylases 65 and 67 (GAD65/67; **a-c**; magenta), vGLUT2 (**d-f**; green),
56 and its merge (**g-i**). Arrowhead indicated focal clusters of larger immunopositive
57 puncta. High-magnification details of GAD65/67 (**j-l**), vGLUT2 (**m-o**) and its merge (**p-**
58 **r**) are shown for VPM, Po dorsal and Po ventral domains. Bregma coronal level (in
59 mm) is indicated above. Scale bars: a-i 250 μ m; j-r 10 μ m.

60

61 **Figure 5. Distribution of glutamatergic subcortical, GABAergic axon terminals**
62 **and L5 axons within Po.** High-resolution confocal images showing in Rbp4-

63 Cre;tdTom+ mice the distribution of vGLUT2 (**a-c**; green), GAD65/67 (**d-f**; blue),
64 tdTomato (L5 labeled cells; **g-i**; magenta) and its merge (**j-l**). Noted that regions rich in
65 vGLUT2 and GAD65/67 are complementary to those where L5 cortical axons are
66 located. Bregma coronal level (in mm) is indicated on the left. Scale bars: 250 μ m.

67

68 **Figure 6. Schematic representation of the location of retrograde tracer deposits.**

69 Location of the six retrograde tracer deposit in Po (**a**; Po1, FB; Po2- Po6, FG) and in
70 VPM (**b**; VPM1, FB; VPM2, FG). Epifluorescence images showing the center of the
71 deposit are shown in the left. Bregma coronal level of each section (in mm) is indicated
72 in the upper right corner. Scale bars: 250 μ m. Deposits were drawn overlaying
73 microphotographs in all Po coronal sections of Franklin and Paxinos atlas (2012) and
74 they were represented with halo and central zone. Only half sections are shown.
75 Anteroposterior, dorsoventral and mediolateral coordinates are indicated above, on the
76 right or below, respectively. Adjacent serial sections were stained with cytochrome
77 oxidase histochemistry to delimit thalamic nuclei.

78

79 **Figure 7. Corticothalamic projections to VPM and Po thalamic nuclei.**

80 Epifluorescence microphotographs showing retrogradely stained neuron somatas in a
81 coronal section of the cerebral cortex in a deposit located in VPM (a) and in Po (b). (c)
82 High-magnification detail of L5b corticothalamic labeled cells. (d) High-magnification
83 detail of L6 corticothalamic labeled cells. (e) Cortical column details showing the
84 corticothalamic input patterns in S1BF, S1mw, M1 and S2. (f) Location of ipsilateral
85 retrogradely labeled cortical neurons was represented on three flat maps (see Methods)
86 in each case: L5b (magenta), L6a (blue) and L6b (green). Cortical areas and bregma
87 level (arrowhead) are indicated on upper left corner map. Flat map was made using
88 coronal sections of Franklin and Paxinos atlas (2007). Position of cells in each coronal
89 section are plotted along a horizontal line. Abbreviations: BF, barrel field; Cg1,
90 cingulate cortex; Ect, ectorhinal area; FL, forelimb; HL, hindlimb; Ins, insular area; J,
91 jaw; M1-M2, motor area; mv, micro vibrissae; Prh, perirhinal area; S1, primary
92 somatosensory area; S2, secondary somatosensory area; Tr, trunk; ULp: upper lip.
93 Scale bars: a, b 250 μm ; c, d 25 μm ; e 150 μm .

94

95 **Figure 8. Corticothalamic projections to different Po domains.**

96 (a) Schematic representation of location of the retrograde tracer deposits analyzed in
97 this study (Po1-Po6, VPM1-VPM2). Dorsoventral and mediolateral coordinates are
98 indicated on the right or below, respectively. Bregma coronal level of each section is
99 indicated on the lower right corner. (b) Location of ipsilateral retrogradely labeled
100 cortical neurons represented on three “flat maps” in each case: L5b (magenta)
101 superficial L6 (blue) and deep L6 (green). Conventions as in figure 7.

102

103 **Figure 9. Subcortical afferent inputs to Po.**

104 Epifluorescence microphotographs showing retrogradely stained neuron somatas in the
105 ipsilateral reticular thalamic nucleus (TRN; a), zona incerta (ZI; b), anterior pretectal
106 nucleus (APT; c), superior colliculus (SC; d), and contralateral principal (PrV; e, f) and
107 interopolaris spinal (SpVI; i) trigeminal nuclei, gracilis nucleus (Gr; h) and dorsal horn
108 of spinal cord (i). Arrows indicate labeled somatas. High-magnification details are
109 shown on the right corner. Adjacent serial sections were stained with cytochrome
110 oxidase histochemistry for delimitation. Bregma coronal level of each section (in mm)

111 is indicated on the coronal section schema. Other abbreviations: CuR: cuneatus nucleus,
112 rotundus part; DMSpV, dorsomedial spinal trigeminal nucleus; DpG, deep gray layer;
113 Gr: gracilis nucleus; InG, intermediate gray layer; InWh, intermediate white layer; Op,
114 optic tract; PrV-DM, principal trigeminal nucleus, dorsomedial part; PrV-VL, principal
115 trigeminal nucleus, ventrolateral part; ZId, dorsal division of ZI; ZIv, ventral division of
116 ZI. Scale bars: **a-i** 250 μm , insets 25 μm .

117

118 **Figure 10. Summary of subcortical projections to Po and VPM thalamic nuclei.**

119 Schematic summary of the relative abundance of retrogradely labeled cells in the
120 forebrain, midbrain, hindbrain and spinal cord in all cases analyzed in this study.
121 Ipsilateral (I) and contralateral (C) projections are represented separately for each case.
122 Relative abundance of labeled cells is represented by shades of gray. Asterisks indicate
123 the glutamatergic structures (red) and GABAergic structures (blue) that were quantified
124 in this study.

125

126 **Figure 11. AAV tracing of axonal projections from regions afferent to Po.**

127 Single two-photon tomography images from AAV tracing experiments from the Mouse
128 Connectivity Projection dataset (Allen Institute for Brain Science, 2011). Large viral
129 injections at the anterior pretectal nucleus (APT; **a**), the zona incerta (ZI; **c**), the
130 interpolaris part of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVI; **e**), and the superior colliculus
131 (SC; **g**). Images showing the distribution of anterograde axonal labeling in the posterior
132 nucleus of the thalamus are presented in **b**, **d**, **f** and **h**, respectively. Bregma coronal
133 level (in mm) is indicated on the top right corner. Abbreviations: CL, central lateral
134 nucleus; PC, paracentral nucleus; PF, parafascicular nucleus; VL, ventrolateral nucleus;
135 VPM, ventral posteromedial nucleus; ZId, dorsal zona incerta; ZIv, ventral zona incerta;
136 DpG, deep gray layer; InG, intermediate gray layer; InWh, intermediate white layer;
137 Op, optic tract. Scale bars: 1000 μm (a, c, e, g); 500 μm (b, d, f, h). Experiments from
138 the Mouse Connectivity Projection dataset can be found in
139 <http://connectivity.brain-map.org/projection/experiment/278401778> (a-b), 301539438
140 (c-d), 272738620 (e-f), and 128001349 (g-h).

141

142

143 **Figure 12. Axonal arborizations in Po arising from subcortical glutamatergic**
144 **structures.**

145 Microphotographs showing location of 3% BDA micro-iontophoretic injection sites in
146 the cuneatus (Cu; **a**) and gracilis (Gr; **c**) nuclei, in ventrolateral part of principal
147 trigeminal nucleus (PrV-VL; **e**) and the caudalis part of spinal trigeminal nucleus
148 (SpVC; **g**). Sections were counterstained with cytochrome oxidase. Bregma coronal
149 level of each section is indicated on the upper right corner. Confocal images of double
150 immunofluorescence labeling of BDA axons (red) and vGLUT2 terminals (green) in Cu
151 (**b**), Gr (**d**), PrV-VL (**f**) and SpVC (**h**) cases. Insets are represented as white squares.
152 High magnification detail is shown for each case. Arrowhead indicate BDA axonal
153 varicosities immunopositive for vGLUT2. Scale bars: a, c, e, g 250 μm ; b, d, f, h 100
154 μm ; insets 25 μm .

155

156 **Figure 13. Axonal varicosity distribution in Po arising from subcortical**
157 **glutamatergic structures.**

158 Schematic representation of the location of synaptic boutons in Po and adjacent
159 thalamic nuclei, plotted from the anterograde axonal labeling of 3% BDA micro-
160 iontophoretic injection sites in ventrolateral region of principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-
161 VL; **a**), the caudalis part of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVC; **b**), gracilis nucleus
162 (Gr; **c**), cuneatus nucleus (Cu; **d**), cervical spinal cord (**e**) and superior colliculus (SC;
163 **f**). Bregma coronal level (in mm) is indicated above. Individual axonal varicosities in Po
164 are represented as red circles, and axonal varicosities outside Po nucleus are represented
165 in gray color. Abbreviations: Ang, angular thalamic nucleus; LD, laterodorsal nucleus;
166 LP, lateral posterior nucleus; LPM, lateral posterior nucleus, medial part; LPL, lateral
167 posterior nucleus, lateral part; PC, paracentral nucleus; PF, parafascicular nucleus; VL,
168 ventrolateral nucleus; VPM, ventral posteromedial nucleus. Scale bar: 250 μm .

169

170 **Figure 14. Axonal arborizations in Po arising from thalamic reticular nucleus.**

171 Microphotographs showing 3% BDA micro-iontophoretic injection sites in a dorsal (**a**)
172 and ventral (**c**) portion of the reticular thalamic nucleus (TRN). Microphotographs of
173 the details of their respective axonal arborizations in Po are represented in panels **b** and
174 **e**, respectively. Sections were counterstained with cytochrome oxidase. Bregma coronal
175 level of each section is indicated on the upper right corner. Correspondence drawings of

176 the axonal varicosities locations in each section are shown in **c** and **f**. Individual axonal
177 varicosities in Po are represented as red circles, and axonal varicosities outside Po
178 nucleus are represented in gray color. Scale bars: a, c, d, f 250 μm ; b, e 100 μm .

179

180 **Figure 15. Axonal varicosity size of glutamatergic structures innervating Po.**

181 Microphotographs showing examples of axonal varicosities from cortical layer (L)6a
182 (**a**), oralis spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVO; **b**), cortical L5b (**c**) and ventrolateral part of
183 the principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-VL; **d**) in Po. Scale bars: 10 μm . (**e**) Size
184 distribution of axonal varicosities in Po from different cortical and subcortical
185 glutamatergic structures. Axonal varicosities were grouped into discrete intervals
186 according to their maximal cross-sectional area. (**f**) Box-plot diagram showing axonal
187 varicosity sizes of all glutamatergic structures innervating Po. Other abbreviations:
188 SpVC, caudalis spinal trigeminal nuclei; Cu, cuneatus; Gr, gracilis; SC, superior
189 colliculus; SpVI, interpolaris spinal trigeminal nucleus; PrV-DM, dorsomedial part of
190 the principal trigeminal nucleus.

191

192 **Figure 16. Axonal varicosity size of GABAergic structures innervating Po.**

193 Microphotographs showing examples of axonal varicosities from the inhibitory
194 structures that innervate Po: anterior pretectal nucleus (APT; **a**), zona incerta (ZI; **b**) and
195 different cases of thalamic reticular nucleus (TRN) innervating VPM and Po. Scale bar:
196 10 μm . (**e**) Box-plot diagram showing axonal varicosity sizes. (**f**) Size distribution of
197 axonal varicosities grouped into discrete intervals according to their maximal cross-
198 sectional area.

199

200 **Figure 17. Quantitative estimation of local input convergence in Po**

201 (**a**) Schematic representation of location of the retrograde tracer deposits analyzed in
202 this study (Po1-Po6, VPM1-VPM2). Bregma coronal level of each section is indicated
203 on the lower left corner. (**b**) Quantification of cortical L5b (white color) and
204 glutamatergic subcortical (superior colliculus + sensory brainstem + spinal cord relay
205 structures; gray color) labeled cells expressed as Fraction of Labeled Neurons (FLN)
206 percentage in all cases. (**c**) Quantification of inhibitory retrogradely labeled cells in
207 anterior pretectal nucleus (APT, white color), substantia nigra pars reticulata (SNR,
208 black color), zona incerta (ZI, dashed color) and reticular thalamic nucleus (TRN, gray

209 color) expressed as FLN percentage in all cases. **(d)** Labeled cortical L5b cells FLN
210 percentage per cortical area in each case. **(e)** Labeled glutamatergic subcortical cells
211 FLN percentage per nuclei in each case. Cortical areas or nuclei showing less than 2%
212 of labeled cells were grouped in “Others”. **(f)** Correlation between the number of
213 retrogradely labeled cells in the extra-reticular inhibitory structures (ETI; APT + ZI +
214 SNR) and the glutamatergic subcortical structures in all Po cases. **(g)** Correlation
215 between the number of retrogradely labeled cells in ETI structures and cortical L5b in
216 Po cases. Correlations are indicated by linear regression as well as by the coefficient of
217 correlation (R^2). Other abbreviations: S1, primary somatosensory cortex; S2, secondary
218 somatosensory cortex; SC, superior colliculus; VC, vestibular complex, PrV, principal
219 trigeminal complex; SpV, spinal trigeminal complex, DCN, dorsal column nuclei.

220

221 **Figure 18. Distribution of inputs to the posterior thalamic nucleus.**

222 Cartoon diagram of the regions targeted by the various input systems to Po. The
223 delineation is based on immunolabeling and tracing data. Higher color saturation is used
224 to indicate regions with more densely packed terminals. Empty areas indicate regions
225 containing few or no terminals. **(a)** Thalamic reticular nucleus (TRN) and layer 6 (L6)
226 corticothalamic inputs cover the whole extent of Po in homogeneous fashion. **(b)**
227 Cortical layer 5B inputs. **(c)** Territories targeted by axons from dorsal column nuclei
228 (DCN), spinal cord, trigeminal complex or intermediate/deep layers of the superior
229 colliculus (SC). **(d)** Territories targeted by zona incerta (ZI) and anterior pretectal
230 nucleus (APT). For size comparison, a typical mouse Po neuron (Porrero et al., 2016) is
231 shown at the same scale, in the central panel. Scale bar 250 μ m.

Extended data figure legend

232

233

234 **Extended figure 4-1. Distribution of GABA immunolabeled axons in Po.**

235 Microphotographs showing in three different coronal sections of Po the distribution of
236 terminals marked by immunohistochemistry against GABA. Note that in Po there are
237 GABA-positive axon bundles in the rostral and dorsal domains, but the
238 immunolabelling is heavier in the adjacent ventral posteromedial (VPM) or
239 parafasciular (PF) nuclei. Bregma coronal level (in mm) is indicated on the upper right
240 corner. Scale bars: a-c 250 μm .

241

242 **Extended Figure 8-1. Summary of corticothalamic inputs to Po and VPM thalamic** 243 **nuclei.**

244 Schematic summary of the relative abundance of retrogradely labeled cells in L5b
245 (magenta), superficial L6 (blue) and deep L6 (green) from different cortical areas in all
246 cases analyzed in this study (Po1-Po6, VPM1-VPM2). Asterisks indicate presence of
247 contralateral corticothalamic inputs. Abbreviations: Tr, trunk; HL, hindlimb; FL,
248 forelimb; DZ, disgranular zone; BF, barrel field; mv, microvibrissae; J, jaw; ULp: upper
249 lip; Ect, ectorhinal area; Ins, insular cortex; M1-M2, motor area; S1, primary
250 somatosensory area; S2, secondary somatosensory area.

251

252 **Extended Figure 12-1. Axonal arborizations in Po arising from subcortical** 253 **glutamatergic structures.**

254 Microphotographs showing location of 3% BDA (10kDa) micro-iontophoretic injection
255 sites in the dorsomedial region of principal trigeminal nucleus (PrV-DM; **a**), oralis
256 (SpVO; **c**) and interpolaris (SpVI; **e**) part of spinal trigeminal nucleus, parabrachial
257 nuclei (PB; **g**), superior colliculus (SC; **i**) and cervical level of spinal cord (**k**). Details of
258 the axonal arborizations in Po arising from PrV-DM (**b**), SpVO (**d**), SpVI (**f**), PB (**h**),
259 SC (**j**) and spinal cord (**l**) are shown. In each section insets are indicated as white
260 squares. Higher-magnification details of the axonal arborizations in Po are represented
261 on the right. Sections were counterstained with cytochrome oxidase. Bregma coronal
262 level of each section is indicated on the upper right corner. Scale bars: a, c, e, g, i, k 250
263 μm ; b, d, f, h, j, l 100 μm ; insets 25 μm .

264

265 **Extended Figure 13-1. Axonal varicosity distribution in Po arising from**
266 **subcortical glutamatergic structures.**

267 Schematic representation of the location of synaptic boutons in the posterior thalamic
268 nucleus and adjacent thalamic nuclei, plotted from the anterograde axonal labeling of
269 3% BDA micro-iontophoretic injection sites in dorsomedial region of principal
270 trigeminal nucleus (PrV-DM; **a**), the oralis part of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVO;
271 **b**), and the interpolaris part of the spinal trigeminal nucleus (SpVI; **c**). Bregma coronal
272 level (in mm) is indicated above. Individual axonal varicosities in Po are represented as
273 red circles, and axonal varicosities outside Po nucleus are represented in gray color.
274 Abbreviations: Ang, angular thalamic nucleus; LD, laterodorsal nucleus; LP, lateral
275 posterior nucleus; LPM, lateral posterior nucleus, medial part; LPL, lateral posterior
276 nucleus, lateral part; PC, paracentral nucleus; PF, parafascicular nucleus; PVL,
277 ventrolateral nucleus; VPM, ventral posteromedial nucleus. Scale bar: 250 μ m.

278

279 **Extended figure 14-1. Axonal arborizations in Po arising from GABAergic**
280 **structures.**

281 Microphotographs showing 3% BDA (10kDa) micro-iontophoretic injection sites in the
282 anterior pretectal nuclei (**a**) and in the dorsal (ZId; **d**) and ventral (ZIV; **g**) portion of the
283 zona incerta. Microphotographs of the details of their respective axonal arborizations in
284 Po are represented in panels **b**, **e** and **h**, respectively. High-magnification detail of these
285 axonal arborizations is represented as an inset in the lower left corner (white squares).
286 Sections were counterstained with cytochrome oxidase. Bregma coronal level of each
287 section is indicated on the upper right corner. Correspondence drawings of the axonal
288 varicosities locations in each section are shown in **c**, **f** and **i**. Individual axonal
289 varicosities in Po are represented as red circles, and axonal varicosities outside Po
290 nucleus are represented in gray color. Scale bars: a, c, d, f, g, i 250 μ m; b, e, h 100 μ m,
291 insets 25 μ m.